

Urokinase or urokinase-type plasminogen activator (uPA) (PLAU) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : Urokinase, encoded by PLAU, was originally isolated from human urine, and it is also present in the blood and in the extracellular matrix of many tissues. The primary physiological substrate of this enzyme is plasminogen, which is an inactive form (zymogen) of plasmin. Further, activation of plasmin instigates a proteolytic cascade that participates in thrombolysis or extracellular matrix degradation. It has been implicated in atherosclerotic aneurysm formation, Alzheimer disease, radioresistant oesophageal cancer, extravillous trophoblast cell invasion in pregnancy, prostate cancer, coal miners' pneumoconiosis, ErbB2-positive breast cancer, Quebec platelet disorder, colon cancer, chemoresistance of bladder cancer, glioblastoma multiforme, keratinocyte wound healing, psoriasis and basal cell carcinoma, Gaucher disease, obesity-induced type 2 diabetes, hepatocellular carcinoma, bone marrow stromal cells, hypertension, hyperglycemia, SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19 infection, cervical cancer, laryngeal squamous cell carcinoma, pulpitis and aging and aging-related diseases, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic

*ML discoveries of PLAU synergy in Meningiomas

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factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of PLAU, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: PLAU, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective memberanes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Urokinase or urokinase-type plasminogen activator (uPA) (PLAU)

It had been established that human plasma contained an active fibrinolytic and proteolytic enzyme (plasmin), its inactive precursor (plasminogen), and also an inhibitor

(antiplasmin) which over-neutralizes the enzyme (Christensen and MacLeod [13]). Macfarlane and Pilling [14] reported that plasmin and plasminogen were associated with the globulin fraction and antiplasmin with the albumin. Further, fibrinolytic activity could be induced in plasma by the addition of chloroform, which destroyed antiplasmin, or of streptokinase, which activated plasminogen. They list literature were activity also occurred spontaneously in human subjects who have suffered surgical operation, fear, trauma, the injection of adrenalin or strenuous exercise.

It was Sobel et al. [15] that named the enzyme.

Salerno et al. [16] obtained monoclonal antibodies that recognized either the A or B chain of human urinary urokinase. They reported that these antibodies identified human urokinase-producing cells and the product of urokinase mRNA. They observed that the pro-urokinase appeared to be the precursor of both A and B chains of human urinary urokinase. Further, urokinase mRNA in human kidney constituted only 0.1% less of total poly(A)+ RNA.

After treatment with endoproteinase Glu-C (*Staphylococcus aureus* V8 proteinase) Lijnen et al. [17] found that recombinant single-chain urokinase-type plasminogen activator (rscu-PA) was quantitatively converted to two-chain urokinase-type plasminogen activator (rtcu-PA-Glu¹⁵⁸). In rscu-PA, the plasmin-sensitive peptide bond Lys¹⁵⁸-Ile¹⁵⁹ is destroyed by site-specific mutagenesis of Lys¹⁵⁸ to Glu (rscu-PA-Glu¹⁵⁸). They concluded that the amino acid in position 158 was a main determinant of the functional properties of single-chain urokinase-type plasminogen activator but not of the two-chain form.

1.3. Roles of PLAU in different disease

Indirect evidence suggests that matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) and plasminogen activators (PAs) are involved in **atherosclerotic aneurysm formation** and rupture of aortic aneurysms is a major cause of death. MMPs are secreted as inactive zymogens (pro-MMPs), that require activation in the extracellular compartment. Analysis of atherosclerotic aorta by Carmeliet et al. [18], in mice with a deficiency of apolipoprotein E (APOE^{-/-}), singly or combined with a deficiency of tissue-type plasminogen activator (t-PA) (APOE^{-/-}:PLAT^{-/-}) or of urokinase-type plasminogen activator (u-PA) (APOE^{-/-}:PLAU^{-/-}), indicated that deficiency of u-PA protected against media destruction and aneurysm formation, probably via means of reduced plasmin-dependent activation of pro-MMPs. Their genetic evidence pointed that plasmin was a pathophysiologically significant activator of pro-MMPs in vivo and might have implications for the design of therapeutic strategies to prevent aortic-wall destruction by controlling PLAU gene function.

uPA converts plasminogen to plasmin and the later is involved in processing of amyloid precursor protein and degrades secreted and aggregated amyloid- β , a hallmark of **Alzheimer disease** (AD). PLAU, the gene encoding uPA, maps to chromosome 10q22.2 between two regions showing linkage to late-onset AD (LOAD). Sobel et al. [15] genotyped a frequent C/T SNP in codon 141 of PLAU (P141L) in 347 patients with LOAD and 291 control subjects. Thus they concluded that PLAU was a promising new candidate gene for LOAD, with allele C (P141) being a recessive risk allele or allele T (L141) conferring protection.

Radiation therapy is used for the treatment of **oesophageal cancer**. Radioresistance means resistant to the effects of radiation and the term is used in medicine to describe tumors or tissues that are not easily damaged or killed by radiation therapy. Further, it also signifies organisms that can withstand high levels of radiation exposure. Fukuda et al. [19] established radioresistant cell lines by applying fractionated irradiation to identify differentially expressed genes between parent and radioresistant cells. They treated 6 oesophageal cancer cell lines (TE-2/5/9/13, KYSE-170/180) with continuous 2 Gy fractionated irradiation (total dose 60 Gy) and compared expression profiles of each parent and radioresistant lines on a cDNA microarray consisting of 21168 genes. They were able to establish four radioresistant sublines (TE-2R/9R/13R, KYSE-170R), in the fractionated irradiation trial, and identified 19 upregulated and 28 downregulated genes common to radioresistant sublines. PLAU, involved in blood coagulation and cell growth was found to be upregulated. Further, RT-PCR confirmed that genes selected by cDNA microarray were overexpressed in clinical specimens of radioresistant cases.

Extravillous trophoblast cell (EVT) invasion in early **pregnancy** occurs in a relatively low-oxygen environment. Lash et al. [20] obtained placental samples (8-10, 12-14, and 16-20 week gestation) from women undergoing elective surgical termination of pregnancy or after cesarean section delivery and assessed EVT invasion from placental explants cultured at 3/8/20-% oxygen using Matrigel invasion assays. They observed that culture at 3% oxygen inhibited EVT invasion and PLAU receptor and plasminogen activator inhibitor-2 protein levels increased and PLAU activity decreased in these cultures. They concluded that the inhibition of invasive capacity of EVT cultured at 3% oxygen appeared to be mediated both by alterations in levels (a general inhibition) of components the PLAU system and a decrease in the number of cells available to invade.

Helenius et al. [21] analysed 63 locally recurrent hormone-refractory tumours and 78 hormone-refractory metastases from 29 patients who died from **prostate cancer**, to evaluate the frequency of PLAU gene amplification and the sensitivity of prostate cancer cells to PLAU inhibition. They observed that 21% had an increased copy number of PLAU in the locally recurrent hormone-refractory tumours and 31% of the metastases had increased copy number. Further, using two PLAU inhibitors, B428 and p-aminobenzamidine, they found that invasion of a prostate cancer cell line containing PLAU gene amplification was inhibited, while invasion of prostate cell lines without PLAU gene amplification were not.

In 153 healthy volunteers and 154 retired coal miners with **coal miners' pneumoconiosis** (CWP), Chang et al. [22] assessed the gene polymorphisms of missense C/T polymorphism in exon 6 of PLAU gene (PLAU P141L), Alu-repeat in intron 8 of the tissue-type plasminogen activator (PLAT) gene (PLAT TPA25 Alu insertion), and 4G/5G in the promoter region of the serine proteinase inhibitor, clade E (SERPINE) or plasminogen activator inhibitor type 1 gene (SERPINE1-675 4G/5G). Among the CWP subjects, there were 94 individuals with simple pneumoconiosis and 60 individuals with progressive massive fibrosis presenting with worse pulmonary function. By assessing duration of work and its interaction with genotypes via means of logistic regression, they found the missense C/T polymorphism in exon 6 of the PLAU gene to be an effect modifier of the association between work duration and the development of progressive massive fibrosis.

Urban et al. [23] measured 60 genes via qRT-PCR and found PLAU mRNA expression to be the most significant marker in patients with **ErbB2-positive breast cancer** tumors. After evaluation of 898 breast cancer patients, they found that PLAU mRNA expression emerged as a powerful prognostic indicator in ErbB2-positive tumors. Their results were consistent among three independent study populations assayed using different techniques.

Quebec platelet disorder (QPD) is an autosomal dominant disorder with high penetrance and associated with increased risks for bleeding. The hallmark of QPD is a gain-of-function defect in fibrinolysis due to increased platelet content of uPA, without systemic fibrinolysis. Via genetic marker analyses, Diamandis et al. [24], found that QPD was significantly linked to a 2-Mb region on chromosome 10q containing PLAU. Further, their analyses of uPA mRNA indicated that QPD increased transcript levels of the linked PLAU allele with megakaryocyte differentiation and concluded that their results implicated a mutation in an uncharacterized cis element near PLAU as the cause of QPD.

Ribosome-inactivating stresses possess a potent regulatory activity against tumor cell progression. Yang et al. [25] demonstrated that macrophage inhibitory cytokine-1 (MIC-1) and its associated signals determined the **colon cancer** cell response to the chemical ribotoxic stress. They found that the ribotoxic stress agent anisomycin-induced MIC-1 gene expression was involved in the ribotoxin-induced apoptotic pathway. Further, MIC-1 was also a critical inducer of apoptosis-related gene products such as activated PLAU and PLAU receptor (uPAR). On repressing MIC-1 or PLAU action in the tumor cells, they observed that the chemical ribotoxic stress triggered a survival-related MAP kinase such as ERK.

Chemoresistance inhibits cancer chemotherapy. To define the role of the DNA methylation-regulated microRNA (miR) genes in the **chemoresistance of bladder cancer (BCa)**, Lv et al. [26] performed both DNA methylomic and miRomic analyses of a multi-chemosensitive (5637) versus a multi-chemoresistant (H-bc) cell line. They found that miR-193a-3p was hypermethylated/silenced in 5637 and hypomethylated/expressed in H-bc cells. Further, they observed that miR-193a-3p, but not -5p contributed to the BCa's multi-chemoresistance, although both expressed in a same pattern. Also, both PLAU and HIC2 were the true direct targets of miR-193a-3p in BCa cells and it was observed that SRSF2, PLAU and HIC2, worked in concert to relay the miR-193a-3p's impact on the BCa chemoresistance by modulating the activities of 5 signaling pathways, namely - DNA damage, NOTCH, NF- κ B, MYC/MAX, and Oxidative Stress.

Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) is the most common type of brain tumors and the mesenchymal phenotype is the hallmark of tumor aggressiveness in GBMs. Zhong et al. [27] found HMGA2 highly expressed in mesenchymal subtype of GBMs and labeled both glioma perivascular smooth muscle cells (pericytes) and glioma-initiating cells (GICs). This was confirmed as depletion of HMGA2 in GICs resulted in compromised self-renewal and tumorigenic capability, as well as undermined mesenchymal or pericyte differentiation. They further showed that HMGA2 allowed expressions of FOXM1 and PLAU to maintain GIC propagation, gliomagenesis and aggressiveness both in vitro and in vivo.

Epigenetic regulation plays an important role in skin wound healing. Previously

it was found that histone H3K27me3 demethylase JMJD3 regulated inflammation and cell migration in **keratinocyte wound healing**. In their next study, Na et al. [28] identified NOTCH1 as a direct target of JMJD3 and NF- κ B in wounded keratinocytes. They found that NOTCH1 was up-regulated in the wound edge and its expression dependent on JMJD3 and NF- κ B in wounded keratinocytes. Further, they also found that NOTCH1 activated the expression of RhoU and PLAU gene, with the evidence that depletion of RhoU or PLAU resulted in delayed wound closure. In conclusion, they observed that JMJD3 and NF- κ B-mediated NOTCH1 activation was required for the regulation of focal adhesion, floppodia, and stress fiber formation though RhoU and PLAU gene expression, which led to keratinocyte migration during the early phase of skin wound healing.

Evidence exists that implicates the urokinase system in tissue remodeling during neo-vascularization, inflammation, tumor invasion, and metastasis. **Psoriasis and basal cell carcinoma (BCC)** are the most common skin diseases and their pathogenesis is associated with keratinocyte hyperproliferation, inflammatory cell migration, and angiogenesis—processes in which the plasminogen system (uPA (PLAU), uPAR (PLAUR), tissue-type plasminogen activator (tPA), and plasminogen activator inhibitor-1 (PAI-1)) play a crucial role. In the biopsies of patients with psoriasis vulgaris, and BCC, Rubina et al. [29] carried out a comparative analysis of uPA, uPAR, tPA, and PAI-1 expression in the normal skin. They found that PLAUR, PLAUR, and PAI-1 expression were up-regulated in the epidermis of psoriatic skin and in tumor cells in BCC. They detected increased PLAUR expression in the derma of psoriatic lesions and in the stroma surrounding tumor cells in BCC, while increased expression of PLAUR in epidermal cells in psoriasis and in tumor cells in BCC suggested an important role of the uPA system for aggressively proliferating and invading cells of epidermal origin.

Gaucher disease (GD) is a rare inherited metabolic disease caused by pathogenic variants in the GBA1 gene. Ługowska et al. [30] analysed gene expression profile in cultured skin fibroblasts from GD patients, control individuals and, additionally, patients with Niemann-Pick type C disease (NPC). Using expression microarrays with subsequent validation by qRT-PCR method, they found up-regulation of PLAUR, IFIT1, TMEM158 and down-regulation of ATOH8 and ISLR distinguished GD patients from both NPC patients and healthy controls.

Obesity is a major risk factor for type 2 diabetes due to chronic hepatic inflammation and resultant insulin resistance. Hepatocyte growth factor (HGF) is responsible for resetting hepatic homeostasis after injury following activation by uPA, encoded by the PLAUR. Further, PAI-1 encoded by the SERPINE1, which is a uPA inhibitor and antifibrinolytic agent, is often elevated in obesity and is linked to cardiovascular events. In obese knockout (KO) mice, Coudriet et al. [31] found exhibition of an increase in conversion of latent single-chain HGF to active two-chain HGF, which coincided with an increase in the phosphorylation of the HGF receptor (HGFR or MET, encoded by the MET gene), as well as dampened inflammation. Their results suggested that in addition to its other functions, PAI-mediated inhibition of HGF activation prohibited the resolution of inflammation in the context of **obesity-induced type 2 diabetes**.

Tsai et al. [32] evaluated the prognostic value of serum uPA before surgery in **hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC)** patients receiving curative resection. They observed that patients with liver cirrhosis, hypoalbuminemia, and thrombocytopenia were signif-

icantly more likely to present with elevated uPA levels and concluded that uPA was a clinically relevant biomarker in HCC patients receiving curative resection, with higher expression of uPA being associated with higher mortality.

Bone marrow stromal cells (BMSCs) form the core of the tumor microenvironment in the hematological system. Zhou et al. [33] explored the interaction between uPA system and the leukemia bone marrow microenvironment (BMM). While simulating the BMM in leukemia, in BMSCs-HL60 co-culture model, they found higher expression levels of uPA/PLAU, uPAR/PLAUR, PAI-1 and vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) in BMSCs than those in mono-cultured BMSCs. Their findings demonstrated that the co-culture stimulated the production of uPA/PLAU, uPAR/PLAUR, PAI-1, MMP-9, and VEGF-A by BMSCs.

Hypertension is the major cause of cardiovascular complications and in majority of individuals, the cause of elevated blood pressure (BP) cannot be determined, which impairs optimized therapies and prognosis for individual patients. Matafora et al. [34] investigated the effect of salt on naive hypertensive patients to understand the salt intake-blood pressure relationship. They observed that salt-sensitive patients regulated the renin angiotensin system (RAS) differently from salt-resistant patients, and upregulated proteins like epidermal growth factor (EGF) and PLAU, which are involved in the regulation of epithelial ENaC-dependent sodium reabsorption activity.

Hyperglycemia accelerates endothelial cell senescence which contributes to diabetic complications. Previously, it was demonstrated that AQR was susceptibility gene for type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Next, Wan et al. [35] investigated the role of AQR in hyperglycemia-induced senescence and validated the increased AQR expression in senescent human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs). Further, they performed the transcriptomic analyses of HUVECs with the overexpression and knockdown of the AQR, to explore the mechanism by which AQR regulated the cellular senescence. Out of the identified 52 co-expressed genes that were enriched, they selected PLAU to evaluate its contribution to senescence for its highest strength in the enrichment of the biological process. Next, they demonstrated that the knockdown of PLAU rescued senescence-related phenotypes, inflammation in models induced by AQR or TNF- α and endothelial cell activation. In a first, their findings indicated that AQR/PLAU was a critical signaling axis in the modulation of endothelial cell senescence, thus revealing a novel link between hyperglycemia and vascular dysfunction associated with T2DM.

Cleavage of the furin site in **SARS-CoV-2** spike (S) protein, promotes the entry of virus into host cells through specific angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptors, which accounts for increased transmissibility of **COVID-19**. Plasmin, a protease of fibrinolysis system, cleaves the furin site of γ -subunit of human epithelial sodium channels (ENaCs). Sharing the plasmin cleavage by viral S and host ENaC proteins might competitively inter-regulate SARS-CoV-2 transmissibility and edema resolution via the ENaC pathway. To explore this, Hou et al. [36] analyzed single-cell RNA sequence (scRNA-seq) data sets and found that PLAU, SCNN1G (γ -ENaC), and ACE2 (SARS-CoV-2 receptor) were co-expressed in airway/alveolar epithelial cells. Further, they observed that the expression levels of PLAU and FURIN were significantly higher compared with TMPRSS2 in healthy group and the difference was amplified in both epithelial and immune cells in patients with moderate/severe COVID-19 and SARS-CoV-2 infected airway/alveolar epithelial cell lines.

Gao et al. [37] explored the involvement and transcriptional regulation of PLAU in **cervical cancer**. They observed overexpression of PLAU in cervical cancer and their PLAU knockdown in vitro experiments demonstrated that the migration and invasion of HeLa and HT3 cells were significantly suppressed. Further, they confirmed the core promoter of PLAU and the transcription factor YinYang 1 (YY1) was found to regulate PLAU mRNA expression.

Laryngeal squamous cell carcinoma (LSCC) a type of cancer that develops in the lining of the larynx (voice box), originating from laryngeal squamous cell lesions. Liu et al. [38] explored the role of Wilm's tumor 1-associated protein (WTAP)-mediated N6-methyladenosine (m⁶A) modification in LSCC. In a first, they observed an increase in the expression of WTAP and PLAU in LSCC, and confirmed a positive correlation between them. Further, they found the WTAP regulated PLAU stability via m⁶A modification. Deficiency of WTAP suppressed the migration, invasion, and proliferation of LSCC cells, while the phenotype induced by WTAP knockdown in vitro was rescued by overexpression of PLAU.

Meng et al. [39] investigated the role and underlying mechanisms of microRNA (miRNA)-181b in the inflammatory response in **pulpitis** and determined the miRNA-181b and PLAU expression levels in inflamed human dental pulp tissues (HDPTs) and lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-stimulated human dental pulp cells (hDPCs). They observed a significant decrease in miRNA-181b and an increase in PLAU in HDPTs compared to the healthy controls, and the two factors showed a negative correlation. Further, they found that miRNA-181b directly targeted PLAU, as it mechanistically the AKT/NF- κ B pathway. Their knockdown of PLAU showed reversal of the proinflammatory effect. Finally, their in vivo application of the miRNA-181b agomir to inflamed pulp tissue alleviated inflammation.

Cellular senescence is a hallmark of aging that contributes greatly to **aging and aging-related diseases**. Rao et al. [40] showed that extracellular vesicles from human urine-derived stem cells (USC-EVs) efficiently inhibited cellular senescence in vitro and in vivo. Their proteomic analysis revealed that USC-EVs were enriched with PLAU and tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinases 1 (TIMP1), which contributed to the anti-senescent effects of USC-EVs associated with the inhibition of matrix metalloproteinases, cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 2A (P16^{INK4a}), and cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 1A (P21^{cip1}). Their findings suggested autologous USC-EVs as a promising anti-aging agent by transferring PLAU and TIMP1 proteins.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however,

vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [41] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [42] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [42].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette

scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [43]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [44], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [41] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [41]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [45], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. PLAU related synergies

Note - PLAU was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2nd order combinations of PLAU were recorded.

3.1.1. PLAU - individual genes

The following genes in combination with PLAU showed high rankings - collagen type X alpha 1 chain (COL10A1), proteolipid protein 1 (PLP1), matrilin 4 (MATN4), neuritin 1 (NRN1), RUNX family transcription factor 2 (RUNX2), lysosomal associated membrane protein family member 5 (LAMP5), HIVEP zinc finger 3 (HIVEP3), MBL associated serine protease 1 (MASP1), sarcoglycan epsilon (SGCE), cingulin like 1 (CGNL1), kinesin family member 1A (KIF1A), peroxidase (PXDN), complement C1q like 1 (C1QL1), podocan like 1 (PODNL1), matrilin 3 (MATN3), solute carrier family 6 member 11 (SLC6A11), serpin family F member 1 (SERPINF1), C-type lectin domain containing 10A (CLEC10A), solute carrier family 14 member 2 (SLC14A2), contactin 6 (CNTN6), protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 22 (PTPN22), formin homology 2 domain containing 3 (FHOD3), peripherin (PRPH), Fas apoptotic inhibitory molecule 2 (FAIM2), tensin 3 (TNS3), sodium voltage-gated channel alpha subunit 7 (SCN7A), forkhead box F2 (FOXF2), tetratricopeptide repeat domain 29 (TTC29), thrombospondin 1 (THBS1), integrin subunit alpha 11 (ITGA11), dual oxidase 1 (DUOX1), semaphorin 6D (SEMA6D), luteinizing hormone/choriogonadotropin receptor (LHCGR), retinol binding protein 4 (RBP4), Fraser extracellular matrix complex subunit 1 (FRAS1), shroom family member 3 (SHROOM3), dual oxidase maturation factor 1 (DUOXA1), dual oxidase 2 (DUOX2), fibroblast growth factor 7 (FGF7), milk fat globule EGF and factor V/VIII domain containing (MFGE8), NKD inhibitor of Wnt signaling pathway 1 (NKD1), reticulocalbin 3 (RCN3), forkhead associated phosphopeptide binding domain 1 (FHAD1), neurexophilin 2 (NXPH2), BOC cell adhesion associated, oncogene regulated (BOC), aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 family member L1 (ALDH1L1), secreted frizzled related protein 2 (SFRP2), phosphoinositide-3-kinase regulatory subunit 1 (PIK3R1), spermatogenesis associated 9 (SPATA9), tripartite motif containing 7 (TRIM7), dishevelled associated activator of morphogenesis 2 (DAAM2), cholinergic receptor nicotinic beta 3 subunit (CHRN3), neurotrophic receptor tyrosine kinase 2 (NTRK2), dopamine receptor D2 (DRD2), fasciculation and elongation protein zeta 1 (FEZ1), mohawk homeobox (MKX), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A member 6 (KCNA6), thyroid hormone receptor beta (THRB), ADAM metalloproteinase with thrombospondin type 1 motif 12 (ADAMTS12), phosphotyrosine interaction domain containing 1 (PID1), ABI family member 3 binding protein (ABI3BP), chromosome 10 open reading frame 90 (C10orf90), phosphodiesterase 1C (PDE1C), matrix metalloproteinase 16 (MMP16), tetraspanin 7 (TSPAN7), protein phosphatase 2 regulatory subunit Bbeta (PPP2R2B), exostosin like glycosyltransferase 1 (EXTL1), S100 calcium binding protein B (S100B), collagen type XXVI

alpha 1 chain (COL26A1), ELAV like RNA binding protein 4 (ELAVL4), vascular cell adhesion molecule 1 (VCAM1), frizzled related protein (FRZB), C1q and TNF related 7 (C1QTNF7), 15-hydroxyprostaglandin dehydrogenase (HPGD), coagulation factor II thrombin receptor like 2 (F2RL2), Rho related BTB domain containing 3 (RHOBTB3), EBF transcription factor 1 (EBF1), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 2 (DACT2), myozenin 3 (MYOZ3), somatomedin B and thrombospondin type 1 domain containing (SBSPON), carbonic anhydrase 3 (CA3), sushi, von Willebrand factor type A, EGF and pentraxin domain containing 1 (SVEP1), heat shock protein family A (Hsp70) member 12A (HSPA12A), PDZ domain containing ring finger 4 (PDZRN4), transmembrane protein 130 (TMEM130), microfibril associated protein 4 (MFAP4), nicotinamide N-methyltransferase (NNMT), proline rich transmembrane protein 2 (PRRT2), nephronectin (NPNT), energy homeostasis associated (ENHO), armadillo repeat containing 4 (ARMC4 / ODAD2), carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1C (CPT1C), serine/threonine kinase 32A (STK32A), G protein-coupled receptor 27 (GPR27), microtubule associated protein 6 (MAP6), secretogranin II (SCG2), StAR related lipid transfer domain containing 5 (STARD5), sushi domain containing 5 (SUSD5), homeobox B2 (HOXB2), CD248 molecule (CD248), dynein axonemal heavy chain 12 (DNAH12), purinergic receptor P2Y14 (P2RY14), calcium binding protein 4 (CABP4), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 3A1 (SLCO3A1), BCL2 family apoptosis regulator BOK (BOK), serine rich and transmembrane domain containing 1 (SERTM1), phospholipase C beta 1 (PLCB1), neurotrimin (NTM), regulator of G protein signaling 6 (RGS6), pappalysin 1 (PAPPA), transmembrane protein 119 (TMEM119), dual specificity phosphatase 5 pseudogene 1 (DUSP5P1), adrenoceptor alpha 2C (ADRA2C), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A5, pseudogene (ANKRD20A5P), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), placenta associated 9 (PLAC9), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), membrane metalloendopeptidase (MME), family with sequence similarity 180 member B (FAM180B), DLG associated protein 2 (DLGAP2), matrix metallopeptidase 17 (MMP17), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), ras homolog family member T1 pseudogene 2 (RHOT1P2), phospholipid phosphatase 4 (PLPP4), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A), vitrin (VIT), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A9, pseudogene (ANKRD20A9P), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A11, pseudogene (ANKRD20A11P), teneurin transmembrane protein 3 (TENM3), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937), LMCD1 antisense RNA 1 (LMCD1-AS1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily F member 29, pseudogene (CYP4F29P) and sorting nexin 18 pseudogene 13 (SNX18P13).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of PLAU with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the follow-

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS PLAU									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T PLAU									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
COL10A1 - PLAU	258	346	189	248	PLP1 - PLAU	364	373	376	360
MATN4 - PLAU	327	383	320	206	NRN1 - PLAU	249	230	247	292
RUNX2 - PLAU	172	289	258	302	LAMP5 - PLAU	285	377	343	379
HIVEP3 - PLAU	272	257	264	285	MASP1 - PLAU	252	387	384	362
SGCE - PLAU	261	351	282	282	CGNL1 - PLAU	253	330	257	352
KIF1A - PLAU	378	235	370	281	PXDN - PLAU	212	269	256	97
C1QL1 - PLAU	317	267	222	90	PODNL1 - PLAU	348	362	378	238
MATN3 - PLAU	324	273	364	366	SLC6A11 - PLAU	234	203	340	322
SERPINF1 - PLAU	345	236	321	346	CLEC10A - PLAU	376	337	277	222
SLC14A2 - PLAU	350	259	225	295	CNTN6 - PLAU	283	303	174	221
PTPN22 - PLAU	273	283	224	45	FHOD3 - PLAU	288	372	212	131
PRPH - PLAU	344	361	326	325	FAIM2 - PLAU	200	232	316	223
TNS3 - PLAU	243	253	246	210	SCN7A - PLAU	392	279	392	383
FOXF2 - PLAU	332	334	312	168	TTC29 - PLAU	361	333	353	272
THBS1 - PLAU	367	234	290	299	ITGA11 - PLAU	340	348	349	217
DUOX1 - PLAU	254	353	350	323	SEMA6D - PLAU	268	241	314	229
LHCGR - PLAU	369	294	385	300	RBP4 - PLAU	334	386	391	364
FRAS1 - PLAU	290	316	238	245	SHROOM3 - PLAU	237	302	229	276
DUOXA1 - PLAU	226	158	220	250	DUOX2 - PLAU	351	270	351	356
FGF7 - PLAU	375	357	306	381	MFGE8 - PLAU	269	339	274	311
NKD1 - PLAU	321	318	347	310	RCN3 - PLAU	281	266	324	216
FHAD1 - PLAU	314	260	297	286	NXPH2 - PLAU	304	366	390	387
BOC - PLAU	301	321	377	337	ALDH1L1 - PLAU	176	243	213	244
SFRP2 - PLAU	358	385	184	297	PIK3R1 - PLAU	292	255	251	80
SPATA9 - PLAU	313	359	327	258	TRIM7 - PLAU	225	201	255	270
DAAM2 - PLAU	188	341	375	307	CHRN3 - PLAU	384	314	228	376
NTRK2 - PLAU	333	214	289	305	DRD2 - PLAU	346	329	367	333
FEZ1 - PLAU	240	240	273	197	MKX - PLAU	278	247	303	340
KCNA6 - PLAU	353	375	366	298	THRB - PLAU	270	274	359	207
ADAMTS12 - PLAU	262	237	281	390	PID1 - PLAU	275	374	323	296
ABI3BP - PLAU	329	369	110	287	C10orf90 - PLAU	233	206	345	181
PDE1C - PLAU	267	265	379	275	MMP16 - PLAU	122	312	373	344
TSPAN7 - PLAU	372	249	335	375	PPP2R2B - PLAU	191	286	329	384
EXTL1 - PLAU	277	358	253	190	S100B - PLAU	373	193	388	385
COL26A1 - PLAU	380	315	217	260	ELAVL4 - PLAU	185	264	221	227

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between PLAU VS Individual members.

ing influences - • Individual members w.r.t PLAU with PLAU – > COL10A1 / PLP1 / MATN4 / NRN1 / RUNX2 / LAMP5 / HIVEP3 / MASP1 / SGCE / CGNL1 / KIF1A / PXDN / C1QL1 / PODNL1 / MATN3 / SLC6A11 / SERPINF1 / CLEC10A / SLC14A2 / CNTN6 / PTPN22 / FHOD3 / PRPH / FAIM2 / TNS3 / SCN7A / FOXF2 / TTC29 / THBS1 / ITGA11 / DUOX1 / SEMA6D / LHCGR / RBP4 / FRAS1 / SHROOM3 / DUOXA1 / DUOX2 / FGF7 / MFGE8 / NKD1 / RCN3 / FHAD1 / NXPH2 / BOC / ALDH1L1 / SFRP2 / PIK3R1 / SPATA9 / TRIM7 / DAAM2 / CHRN3 / NTRK2 / DRD2 / FEZ1 / MKX / KCNA6 / THRB / ADAMTS12 / PID1 / ABI3BP / C10orf90 / PDE1C / MMP16 / TSPAN7 / PPP2R2B / EXTL1 / S100B / COL26A1 / ELAVL4 / VCAM1 / FRZB / C1QTNF7 / HPGD / F2RL2 / RHOBTB3 / EBF1 / DACT2 / MYOZ3 / SBSPO / CA3 / SVEP1 / HSPA12A / PDZRN4 / TMEM130 / MFAP4 / NNMT / PRRT2 / NPNT / ENHO / ARMC4 / CPT1C / STK32A / GPR27 / MAP6 / SCG2 / STARD5 / SUSP5 / HOXB2 / CD248 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / CABP4

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS PLAU									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T PLAU									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
VCAM1 - PLAU	302	304	294	359	FRZB - PLAU	299	258	286	271
C1QTNF7 - PLAU	391	382	372	262	HPGD - PLAU	156	220	348	226
F2RL2 - PLAU	312	285	308	345	RHOBTB3 - PLAU	370	391	365	335
EBF1 - PLAU	359	205	380	199	DACT2 - PLAU	336	251	330	144
MYOZ3 - PLAU	251	295	249	228	SBSPON - PLAU	293	276	342	261
CA3 - PLAU	385	291	188	368	SVEP1 - PLAU	319	308	383	319
HSPA12A - PLAU	177	297	319	324	PDZRN4 - PLAU	377	347	352	246
TMEM130 - PLAU	386	392	389	382	MFAP4 - PLAU	183	296	322	264
NNMT - PLAU	338	365	284	341	PRRT2 - PLAU	207	149	210	249
NPNT - PLAU	219	228	252	99	ENHO - PLAU	320	324	309	257
ARMC4 - PLAU	295	360	299	184	CPT1C - PLAU	339	356	334	303
STK32A - PLAU	362	342	144	386	GPR27 - PLAU	206	217	305	142
MAP6 - PLAU	271	245	177	247	SCG2 - PLAU	383	349	337	336
STARD5 - PLAU	308	275	357	232	SUSD5 - PLAU	248	344	248	332
HOXB2 - PLAU	208	350	240	203	CD248 - PLAU	328	283	331	200
DNAH12 - PLAU	306	300	226	320	P2RY14 - PLAU	300	390	215	330
CABP4 - PLAU	322	254	298	160	SLCO3A1 - PLAU	291	327	259	290
BOK - PLAU	315	222	301	233	SERTM1 - PLAU	389	380	386	321
PLCB1 - PLAU	309	221	236	277	NTM - PLAU	337	298	291	351
RGS6 - PLAU	246	367	214	353	PAPPA - PLAU	357	187	341	350
TMEM119 - PLAU	387	340	165	265	DUSP5P1 - PLAU	307	250	179	259
ADRA2C - PLAU	229	335	354	234	PRKD1 - PLAU	318	376	355	274
FLRT2 - PLAU	368	280	209	119	SHC4 - PLAU	232	261	371	176
ANKRD20A5P - PLAU	388	364	292	327	KBTBD12 - PLAU	296	325	267	153
LDLRAD2 - PLAU	331	343	265	289	PLAC9 - PLAU	341	313	310	354
NUGGC - PLAU	266	299	283	219	MME - PLAU	381	354	328	371
MMP17 - PLAU	186	309	382	318	ZNF521 - PLAU	325	223	268	328
RYR3 - PLAU	289	248	261	230	RHOT1P2 - PLAU	342	301	318	343
PLPP4 - PLAU	343	246	356	347	FAM155A - PLAU	161	278	205	306
VIT - PLAU	354	388	304	369	ANKRD20A9P - PLAU	371	381	369	293
GPX3 - PLAU	218	338	293	314	HMGB3P7 - PLAU	335	292	276	349
ANKRD20A11P - PLAU	352	332	262	370	TENM3 - PLAU	390	277	344	355
LINC00937 - PLAU	204	227	245	23	LMCD1-AS1 - PLAU	382	363	325	104
CYP4F29P - PLAU	356	326	317	380	SNX18P13 - PLAU	366	389	332	361

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between PLAU VS Individual members.

/ SLCO3A1 / BOK / SERTM1 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PAPPA / TMEM119 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / FLRT2 / SHC4 / ANKRD20A5P / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / MME / FAM180B / DLGAP2 / MMP17 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / FAM155A / VIT / ANKRD20A9P / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / LINC00937 / LMCD1-AS1 / CYP4F29P / SNX18P13.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic PLAU 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of PLAU-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t PLAU

COL10A1 / PLP1 / MATN4 / NRN1 / RUNX2 ...
 LAMP5 / HIVEP3 / MASP1 / SGCE / CGNL1 ...
 KIF1A / PXDN / C1QL1 / PODNL1 / MATN3 ...
 SLC6A11 / SERPINF1 / CLEC10A / SLC14A2 ...
 CNTN6 / PTPN22 / FHOD3 / PRPH / FAIM2 ...
 TNS3 / SCN7A / FOXF2 / TTC29 / THBS1 ...
 ITGA11 / DUOX1 / SEMA6D / LHCGR / RBP4 ...
 FRAS1 / SHROOM3 / DUOXA1 / DUOX2 / FGF7 ...
 MFGE8 / NKD1 / RCN3 / FHAD1 / NXPH2 / BOC ...
 ALDH1L1 / SFRP2 / PIK3R1 / SPATA9 / TRIM7 ...
 DAAM2 / CHRNB3 / NTRK2 / DRD2 / FEZ1 / MKX ...
 KCNA6 / THRB / ADAMTS12 / PID1 / ABI3BP ...
 C10orf90 / PDE1C / MMP16 / TSPAN7 / PPP2R2B ...
 EXTL1 / S100B / COL26A1 / ELAVL4 / VCAM1 ...
 FRZB / C1QTNF7 / HPGD / F2RL2 / RHOBTB3 ...
 EBF1 / DACT2 / MYOZ3 / SBSPON / CA3 / SVEP1 ...
 HSPA12A / PDZRN4 / TMEM130 / MFAP4 / NNMT ...
 PRRT2 / NPNT / ENHO / ARMC4 / CPT1C / STK32A ...
 GPR27 / MAP6 / SCG2 / STARD5 / SUSD5 / HOXB2 ...
 CD248 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / CABP4 / SLCO3A1 ...
 BOK / SERTM1 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PAPP ...
 TMEM119 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / FLRT2 ...
 SHC4 / ANKRD20A5P / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / PLAC9 ...
 NUGGC / MME / FAM180B / DLGAP2 / MMP17 ...
 ZNF521 / RYR3 / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / FAM155A ...
 VIT / ANKRD20A9P / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P ...
 TENM3 / LINC00937 / LMCD1-AS1 / CYP4F29P ...
 SNX18P13 PLAU

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between PLAU and Individual members.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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